

Improvement of load-bearing performance of lattice shells by torsion-free joints

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Abstract

Lattice shells generated from Edge Offset meshes (EO meshes), referred to as EO lattice shells, possess the property of preventing beam torsion and kinks at the joints. This study investigates the impact of beam torsion and/or joint incompatibility on the load-bearing performance of individual beams and single-layer lattice shells composed of flat steel. First, a single beam is analyzed to assess how the torsional angle at the joint affects axial and bending deformations through geometrically nonlinear analysis. Subsequently, the overall load-bearing performance of a conventional lattice shell including joint torsion (non-EO lattice shell) and an EO lattice shell with torsion-free joints is compared using geometrically nonlinear analysis to evaluate improvement in the load-bearing performance of lattice shells achieved by the properties of EO meshes.

Keywords: lattice shell, joint with geometric torsion, torsion-free joint, edge offset mesh, geometrically nonlinear analysis

1. Introduction

Shell structures that cover large curved architectural spaces are often designed as approximations using lattice shells composed of straight beams arranged in triangular, quadrilateral, hexagonal, or other polygonal patterns. From the perspective of production cost and environmental sustainability, lattice shells often utilize standardized cross-sections, such as flat steel, circular, or box sections. In such structures, the most critical factors affecting cost and constructability are *torsion or kinks at the joints*, where connected beams do not intersect along a common axis or misalignment occurs at the top and bottom ends of the beams, respectively, as shown in Fig. 1. When realizing a curved surface designed by an architect as a lattice shell, arbitrarily placing joints on the surface and connecting them with straight beams often results in the symmetry planes of the beams not intersecting at a single axis at the joint, or in incompatible angles between the joint axis and the beams. This causes torsion or kinks, requiring the fabrication of special joints or the application of twisting processes to the beams, as shown in Fig. 2. These measures increase cost and require advanced production techniques, limiting the available engineers and equipment.

Additionally, when installing finishing materials such as glass, it is essential for the panels enclosed by the beams of the lattice shell to remain planar. However, if the panels are polygons with more than four sides, planarity is generally difficult to be maintained, requiring countermeasures such as using curved glass, which further increases costs and reduces productivity.

To address these issues, Pottmann *et al.* [1] defined an *Edge Offset Mesh (EO mesh)* composed of edges, nodes, and faces. They demonstrated that lattice shells derived from EO meshes can be constructed using beams of uniform height while avoiding torsion, kinks, and non-planarity in the joints, beams and panels. In this study, such lattice shells are referred to as *EO lattice shells*. Additionally, they proposed a method to approximately generate EO meshes.

The authors proposed a method to generate EO meshes using sequential optimization, where the edge lengths are treated as variables while maintaining parallelism with a Möbius-transformed reference mesh [2]. This method enables the precise generation of EO lattice shells that closely approximate the specified surface shapes. Laguerre geometry is also known as a transformation that converts one EO mesh into another EO mesh [3].

While lattice shells with *torsion-free joints* are known to offer superior cost efficiency and construction performance due to the absence of beam eccentricity at each end, to the best of our knowledge, no numerical investigation has been conducted to compare their mechanical performance with that of general *non-EO lattice shells* that include geometric torsion at the joints.

In this study, we investigate the impact of joint torsion on the structural performance of single-layer lattice shell structures composed of flat steel beams using geometrically nonlinear analysis. First, a model consisting of a single beam is analyzed to evaluate how torsional angles at the joints affect axial and bending deformation through geometrically nonlinear analysis. Then, a comparative analysis is conducted between a conventional lattice shell with geometric torsion and a shell composed of torsion-free joints only.

Figure 1: Construction difficulty of joints: (a) torsion, (b) kinks

Figure 2: Examples of joints with torsion

2. Impact of joint torsion on the load-bearing performance of flat steel beams

Here, we examine a single flat steel beam that constitutes a lattice shell, investigating how the torsion occurring between the beam and the joint axis at both ends affects the beam's axial stiffness, buckling resistance in the axial direction, bending stiffness, and buckling resistance in bending.

2.1. Analysis model

The analysis model is shown in Fig. 3. The plate in Fig. 3 represents a lattice shell beam (flat steel with depth d and thickness t) and is defined based on the locations of end nodes A and B, and the joint axis

Figure 3: Analysis model

(referred to as the Node Axis hereafter, depicted as blue and red solid lines in Fig 3) according to the following procedure. Both ends of the beam exhibit torsion of $\theta_T/2$ relative to the Node Axis.

Let $\overline{AB} = L$. For simplicity, we assume that the Node Axes at both ends are perpendicular to line AB. At nodes A and B, points P and Q are located on their respective node offset axes such that $\overline{AP} = \overline{BQ} = d/2$. In general, points A, B, Q, and P do not lie on the same plane, so points A' and B' are determined such that $\angle PAA' = \angle B'BQ$ and the quadrilateral AA'B'B forms a rectangle with dimensions $d \times L$. Additionally, $\angle PAA' + \angle B'BQ = \theta_T/2$.

The rectangle AA'B'B is divided into quadrilateral shell elements arranged in a grid with n_x elements in the x-direction and n_y elements in the y-direction. The element nodes along boundaries AA' and BB' are connected to the representative points P and Q, respectively, with rigid bars. Support conditions are applied to points P and Q as follows (T: translation, R: rotation, 1: fixed, 0: free):

$$P: (T_x, T_y, T_z, R_x, R_y, R_z) = (0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0), \quad Q: (T_x, T_y, T_z, R_x, R_y, R_z) = (1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0)$$

Three analysis cases listed in Table 1 are considered. Here, "*" denotes the constrained degree of freedom, and $\overline{M}_P = \left[*, -M \sin \frac{\theta_T}{2}, M \cos \frac{\theta_T}{2} \right]^T$ and $\overline{M}_Q = \left[*, -M \sin \frac{\theta_T}{2}, -M \cos \frac{\theta_T}{2} \right]^T$. Illustrations of cases A-Msym and A-Masm are shown in Fig. 4.

Table 1: Analysis Case

Case	N	M_P	M_Q
A-N	$[N,*,*]^T$	$[*,0,0]^T$	$[*,0,0]^T$
A-Msym	$[0,*,*]^T$	\overline{M}_P	\overline{M}_Q
A-Masm	$[0,*,*]^T$	\overline{M}_P	$-\overline{M}_Q$

Figure 4: Case A-Msym and A-Masm

The software library OpenSeesPy [4] is used for finite element analysis. The shell elements on the rectangle AA'B'B are modeled using ShellNLDKGQ element (four node flat shell element with membrane and drilling DOF considering geometric nonlinearity) [5], and updated Lagrangean method is used for geometrically nonlinear analysis. Additionally, initial imperfection is introduced as a half-wavelength sinusoidal shape in the z-component of the nodal coordinates on the rectangle AA'B'B, with an amplitude of $a \times L$, where a is a parameter.

We refer to the following geometry conditions as the *Base Model*: $d = 0.30$ [m], $L = 0.70$ [m], $t = 0.009$ [m], $\theta_T = 0.10$ [rad], $a = 1/1000$. Young's modulus E and shear modulus G are 2.05×10^5 [N/mm²] and $E/\{2(1 + \nu)\}$, respectively, where Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.30$. Material nonlinearity is not considered. The rigid bars in Fig. 3 are modeled as beams with a square cross-section of 0.10×0.10 [m], with both the Young's modulus and shear modulus set to 100 times the above values.

The quasistatic equilibrium path is traced using displacement increment analysis. The DisplacementControl integrator is used. For A-N, the control displacement is the x -directional displacement u_P at point P, which is uniformly increased from 0 to $L/400$ over 5000 steps. For A-Msym and A-Masm, the control displacement is the rotational angle θ_{zP} around the z-axis at point P, which is uniformly increased from 0 to $(L/d)/150$ over 5000 steps.

2.2. Effects of torsional angle on axial stiffness and buckling resistance

To investigate the effects of the torsional angle θ_T on axial stiffness and buckling resistance, nonlinear equilibrium path-tracing analyses were conducted for Case A-N across combinations of four torsional angles ($\theta_T = 0.00, 0.05, 0.10, 0.20$ [rad]) and two plate thicknesses ($t = 0.006, 0.009$ [m]) including the Base Model. The results are shown in Fig 5, where the horizontal axis represents u_P and the vertical axis represents the incremental load N . For reference, the Euler buckling load N_c , calculated as shown below, is indicated with a black dashed line in the figure. Here, $I_y = dt^3/12$.

$$N_c = \frac{\pi^2 EI_y}{L^2} \quad (1)$$

From Fig. 5, it can be observed that for all plate thicknesses, the axial stiffness decreases as θ_T increases. The theoretical value of the initial axial stiffness K_0 is given as follows, where $A = td$:

$$K_0 = \frac{EA}{L} \quad (2)$$

Figure 5: Case A-N: (a) $t = 0.006$, (b) $t = 0.009$

Figure 6: Variation of K_T/K_0 with plate thickness and torsional angle

Figure 7: Deformation at the final step (Base Model, magnification $\times 1$)

Figure 6 shows the ratio of the initial axial stiffness K_T , obtained from the numerical analysis results in Fig. 5, to the theoretical value K_0 for each plate thickness t and angle θ_T . From Fig. 6, it can be seen that the ratio of K_T to K_0 decreases as the plate thickness decreases or as θ_T increases. The deformation of the Base Model at the final analysis step is shown in Fig. 7.

2.3. Effects of torsional angle on bending stiffness and buckling resistance

Next, the results for case A-Msym and A-Masm are shown in Figs. 8 and 9. In these figures, the horizontal axis represents θ , which is the average of the absolute values of the rotational angles around the z -axis at points P and Q, while the vertical axis represents the moment M at the beam ends. For reference, the lateral buckling moment M_c , calculated as shown below, is indicated with a black dashed line.

$$M_c = C \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2 E I_y}{L^2} \left(\frac{\pi^2 E I_w}{L^2} + GJ \right)} \quad (3)$$

Here, $J = kdt^3$, where $k = \frac{1}{3} \left\{ 1 - \frac{192}{\pi^5} \frac{t}{d} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^5} \tanh \frac{(2n-1)\pi d}{2t} \right\}$, moment coefficients are $C = 1$ (A-Msym) and $C = 2.75$ (A-Masm), and $I_w = 0$ because warping can be neglected.

As can be seen from Fig. 8, in the single-curvature bending cases A-Msym, the influence of the torsional angle θ_T on the load-deformation curve is small for all plate thicknesses t , and there is no significant difference in the initial slopes and in the region where the moment M exceeds the buckling moment M_c calculated by Eq. (3). However, when the torsional angle θ_T increases to around 0.20, the rotational angle at the buckling point becomes larger.

Figure 8: Case A-Msym: (a) $t = 0.006$, (b) $t = 0.009$

Figure 9: Case A-Masm: (a) $t = 0.006$, (b) $t = 0.009$

Figure 10: Deformation at the final analysis step (Base Model, magnification $\times 1$):
 (a) A-Msym, (b) A-Masm

Similarly, in the double-curvature bending case A-Masm as shown in Fig. 9, the effect of the torsional angle θ_T on the initial slope is small, regardless of plate thickness. However, as θ increases, the slope of the $M - \theta$ curve decreases more significantly than A-Msym for larger θ_T . The deformation of the Base Model at the final analysis step for A-Msym and A-Masm are shown in Fig. 10.

3. Comparison between EO shell and Non-EO shell using nonlinear buckling analysis

Finally, we compare the performances of EO shell and the Non-EO shell shown in Fig. 11 using nonlinear buckling analysis. These shells are generated to conform to the same target surface, a rotational surface around the z -axis, with a bottom circular diameter of 10 [m]. The EO shell is generated using the method described by Watada and Ohsaki [2]. The Non-EO lattice shell is defined by projecting uniform regular hexagons, filled in the plane to fit within a circle at the outer edge and having the same number as the EO lattice shell, vertically onto the target surface to determine the points on the surface and the corresponding node axis as the normal vector of the surface at each point as shown in Fig. 12.

The modeling method for each joint and beam is shown in Fig. 13. The beams with a depth d are generated as follows using the nodal points $X_i(\mathbf{x}_i)$ and $X_j(\mathbf{x}_j)$, as well as the unit offset vectors \mathbf{n}_i and \mathbf{n}_j , which represent the directions of the node axes at their respective positions:

Figure 11: Analysis model: (a) EO lattice shell, (b) Non-EO lattice shell

Figure 12: Generation of a Non-EO lattice shell shape approximating the target surface

Figure 13: Analysis model for each beam

1. Define the representative point P_i and offset node X_i' associated with node X_i , as well as P_j and X_j' associated with node X_j , such that $\overline{X_i P_i} = (d/2)\mathbf{n}_i$, $\overline{X_i X_i'} = d\mathbf{n}_i$, $\overline{X_j P_j} = (d/2)\mathbf{n}_j$ and $\overline{X_j X_j'} = d\mathbf{n}_j$.
2. Consider the plane F_i , which passes through X_i and is orthogonal to $\overline{X_i X_j}$. Determine X_i'' , a point on the line passing through X_i' and perpendicular to plane F_i , such that $\overline{X_i X_i''} = d$. Similarly, define plane F_j and point X_j'' associated with node X_j .
3. Let M be the midpoint of X_i and X_j , and N' the midpoint of X_i'' and X_j'' . Define N such that $\overline{MN} = d\overline{MN'} / |\overline{MN'}|$. Find the intersection of the line passing through N and parallel to $\overline{X_i X_j}$ with planes F_i and F_j , and define these intersection points as X_i''' and X_j''' , respectively. Let the angles satisfy $\angle X_i'' X_i X_i''' = \angle X_j'' X_j X_j''' = \theta_T/2$, and define $\angle X_i' X_i X_i''' = \theta_{Ci}$ and $\angle X_j' X_j X_j''' = \theta_{Cj}$.
4. Offset X_i and X_i''' along $\overline{X_i X_j} / |\overline{X_i X_j}|$ by e to define points U_i and V_i . Similarly, offset X_j and X_j''' along $-\overline{X_i X_j} / |\overline{X_i X_j}|$ to define U_j and V_j .

Using these points, define a local element coordinate system where the x -axis is along $\overline{U_i U_j}$ and the y -axis is along $\overline{U_i V_i}$. The rectangular region $U_i V_i V_j U_j$ is modeled with a grid of quadrilateral shell elements

Figure 14: Comparison of load-displacement relationships between EO Shell and Non-EO Shell

of thickness t , divided into n_x elements in the x -direction and n_y elements in the y -direction. Connect the representative point P_i to the $n_y + 1$ nodes along $\overline{U_i V_i}$ using rigid bars. Similarly, connect P_j to the $n_y + 1$ nodes along $\overline{U_j V_j}$ with rigid bars. Let $\overline{U_i U_j} = l$.

Initial imperfections are introduced at the internal shell nodes as a half-wavelength sinusoidal shape in the z -axis direction with an amplitude of $l/1000$.

In the subsequent analysis, the following parameters are used: $d = 0.300$ [m], $t = 0.006$ [m], $e = 0.010$ [m], $n_x = 4$, $n_y = 3$, $E = 2.05 \times 10^5$ [N/mm²], $\nu = 0.3$. The 12 perimeter supports are simply supported. The uniform vertical loads ΔP [kN] are applied to the representative points of the 6 top nodes as shown in Fig. 11. Geometrical nonlinearity is considered, and the shell elements are modeled using the NLDKGQ elements in OpenSees. Material nonlinearity is not considered. The rigid bars are modeled as beams with a square cross-section of 0.10 [m] \times 0.10 [m], using both Young's modulus E and shear modulus scaled by a factor of 100. The DisplacementControl integrator is used, with the vertical displacement δ at one of the loading points set as the control variable. The increment for each step is adjusted within the range of 10^{-5} to 10^{-2} to satisfy the convergence test criteria, and the analysis is performed accordingly.

From Fig. 14, the initial stiffness of the EO shell is 76.9 [kN/m], which is 1.66 times higher than the initial stiffness of the Non-EO shell, 46.2 [kN/m]. Additionally, the Non-EO shell failed to satisfy the convergence test at $(\delta, \Delta P) = (0.1281, 5.1771)$, and even in a subsequent reference analysis with relaxed convergence conditions, the maximum load was reached at $(\delta, \Delta P) = (0.1998, 8.4128)$. By contrast, the EO shell reaches $(\delta, \Delta P) = (0.2157, 11.3608)$ at the final step of the analysis, demonstrating superior load-bearing performance compared to the Non-EO shell.

4. Conclusion

The findings of this study are summarized as follows:

- A modeling method for lattice shells composed of flat steel beams with torsional joints has been proposed, and the impact of joint torsion on the load-bearing performance of both individual beams and the entire lattice shell has been investigated using geometrically nonlinear analysis.

- Numerical analysis has confirmed that beams connected to joints with torsion exhibit reduced axial stiffness and buckling resistance in the axial direction, as well as lower antisymmetric strong-axis bending stiffness and bending buckling resistance, compared to beams connected to torsion-free joints. Furthermore, these differences in individual beam performance propagate into differences in the overall load-bearing capacity of the lattice shell, as verified through numerical analysis of the entire structure.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by JST CREST JPMJCR1911.

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